

Using BIM to reflect critical project management items

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Abstract

During the construction phase a great exchange of data is required. That exchange of information is made by different stakeholders and related to different phases of the process. The importance and criticality of that information depends on several parameters, but the project manager must act according to each exchange of information. To that it is needed to filter and sort them in such a manner that the project manager has a clear view of all the issues and may decide, keep track or speed up the decision on the most important and critical items to avoid delays and time waste. The industry is still missing a proper prioritization of information and associated tasks and a formal way to display that in a BIM environment to facilitate the view and perspective of the existing status of the ongoing project.

The main purpose of this study is to significantly reduce the time that the project managers spend to prioritize the problems that arise during the construction phase. This is done by automatically presenting the action items in the model based on the volume of information exchange between stakeholders. The thesis objectives are to identify a proper source of communication in a format that can be extracted and kept in records so that it can be used in the future, to have a clear prioritization matrix that can be implemented and to finally reflect criticality of items on the BIM model.

This research offers an attempt to develop a BIM model that will reflect all the items according to its importance and criticality in a fast and easy to understand way such as color

grading of identification: green, yellow and red. Green for items that are not currently critical, yellow for items that should be taken care soon before becoming critical and red for items that are currently critical.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/8muCEGmwNHI>

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